

Reaction of promising breeding lines to major diseases. Punjab Agricultural University, India

MS = moderately susceptible
(Abundant sclerotia visible with partial rotting of stem)

S = susceptible (Abundant sclerotia visible, stem completely rotten)

We found 31 lines to be moderately resistant or resistant to at least one disease. Five were moderately resistant to bacterial blight; 2 were resistant and 12 moderately resistant to sheath blight; 2 were resistant and 10 moderately resistant to sheath rot; and 4 were moderately resistant to stem rot (see table). Of the three lines possessing multiple disease resistance, PAU50-B-25-1 (MR to bacterial blight and sheath blight) and PAU13-8-3-1-1 (MR to sheath blight and sheath rot) have long slender grains with average yields equal to those of Jaya, IR8, and PR106. These two lines have the potential to replace existing semidwarf varieties that have become susceptible to diseases.

A resistant reaction was recorded for 2 lines each against sheath blight and sheath rot, while a moderately resistant reaction was found for 5 lines against bacterial blight, 12 lines against sheath blight, 10 lines against sheath rot, and

Designation	Cross	Reaction ^a			
		Bacterial blight	Sheath blight	Sheath rot	Stem rot
PAU13-8-3-1-1	Basmati 370/IR8	MS	MR	MR	S
PAU13-8-3-6-2-1-2	"	M	M	M	MR
PAU14-3-15-B-8-1-2	IR8/Basmati 370	M	MR	M	MS
PAU29-295-3-B-2-1	Basmati 370/Hamsa	MS	MR	M	MS
PAU41-10-1-3-262-1-5	Phulpattas 72/Mutant 65	MS	R	M	MS
PAU50-B-25-1	Jaya/IR579	MR	MR	M	MS
PAU50-B-51-1-1-20-62-1	"	M	M	MR	MS
PAU122-73-1-4-1	Basmati 370 mutant/Basmati 370	MS	M	R	S
PAU143-B-41-1-1-1	Norin 18/Hybrid 27	MS	MS	MR	S
PAU164-102-1-2-1-1-1	PAU29-108/Palman 579	MS	M	MR	MS
PAU269-1-9-1-3	Sona/Basmati 370	MS	M	M	MR
PAU311-12-2-1	Basmati 370/Basmati 21	MS	M	MR	MS
PAU317-B-2	Jhona 349/Jaya	S	R	M	MS
PAU321-B-19	Palman 579/Basmata 21	MR	M	M	MS
PAU322-B-11	HM95/Basmata 21	MR	M	M	MS
PAU391-B-12	Sabarmati/Ratna	MR	M	M	S
Pusa 37-6-2-3	IR82/BJ 1	MS	MS	R	S
RP633-519-1-3-8-1	IR8/BJ 1//IR22	MR	S	MR	MR
IR5853-229-1	Nam Sagui/IR2071-88//IR2061-214-3-6-20	M	M	MR	S
VI-158	-	MS	M	M	MR
CIAT 4	-	M	MR	M	S
Mehran 69	-	M	MS	MR	MS

^aR = resistant, MR = moderately resistant, M = intermediate, MS = moderately susceptible, S = susceptible.

4 lines against stem rot. The largest number of lines gave at intermediate reaction to bacterial blight, sheath blight, and sheath rot. For stem rot, the largest

number of lines were moderately susceptible. The resistant and moderately resistant breeding lines will be used as donor parents. ■

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Insect resistance

Varietal screening for brown planthopper resistance

T. S. Krishna, reader in botany, A. V. College, Hyderabad, India; D. V. Seshu, plant breeder, International Rice Research Institute; and M. B. Kalode, senior entomologist, All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project (AICRIP), Hyderabad, India

In a greenhouse screening at the AICRIP headquarters, Hyderabad, of 2,360 rice varieties from different sources, 136 were identified as highly resistant and 69 as moderately resistant to the brown planthopper (BPH).

Among those identified as resistant, several were from Northeast India, South India, and Sri Lanka. The highly resistant varieties are listed in the table. ■

Some varieties found highly resistant (score 1) to the brown planthopper in greenhouse tests at All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project, Hyderabad, India.

Variety	Origin	Variety	Origin
Djawa Sredek	Indonesia	Company Chittari	India
Gapita	"	Enna Patta	"
Mawee	Sri Lanka	Kula Peruvula	"
Umsum	Korea	MHL 1	"
Lua Ngu	Vietnam	Pandi	"
Nang Lay	"	Parakulam	"
Nganetic	Laos	Pokkali	"
Lal Dhapa (ARC7327)	India	PTB21	"
IC25 11 3	"	PTB33	"
IC25 172	"	S 61	"
T2755	"	S 2204	"
JBS1168	"	T3	"
Manoharsali	"	T10	"
PTB28	"	T16	"
A-1	"	T27	"
ADT 8	"	T1415	"
AE 1443	"	T1421	"
Chennellu	"	T1465	"
Chenninayakan	"	T1471	"
Cheriya Chittari	"	Vella Chenipan	"